

REACTIVE MIXING OF POLYPROPYLENE/POSS NANOCOMPOSITES. CRYSTALLIZATION, MORPHOLOGY AND THERMAL PROPERTIES

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SUMMARY

The structure and phase behaviour of PP/POSS nanocomposites obtained by reactive blending of maleic anhydride grafted PP and amino functionalized POSS, have been investigated. SEM, EDS, WAXS and DSC analyses showed marked changes in the crystallization behaviour and properties of the samples supporting a molecular dispersion of the filler in the polymer matrix.

Keywords: polypropylene, POSS, nanocomposites, reactive mixing, crystallization

INTRODUCTION

Polymeric hybrids and nanocomposites containing polyhedral oligomeric silsesquioxanes (POSS) - general formula $(\text{RSiO}_{1.5})_p$ where R is an organic group – as dispersed inorganic phase offer the opportunity to design advanced materials with enhanced thermal and mechanical performances. It has been pointed out that the morphology, the thermal stability and tensile properties of thermoplastics (polyolefins, polyesters, polyamides, etc.) containing POSS can be largely affected by the chemical structure, concentration and dispersion degree of POSS nanoparticles [1-3]. The effect of POSS addition on the crystallization process and crystalline structure of polyolefins has been examined under various conditions and it is matter of discussion [4-7].

In general, due to the poor interactions between POSS and most polymer matrices, the presence of coupling agents or even the chemical modification of the components becomes necessary to improve the compatibility of these materials. The polymer/filler interfacial interactions and thus the dispersion of the filler in the polymer matrix are expected to be markedly enhanced by the introduction of functional groups on the POSS molecules, which can interact during melt blending with reactive groups grafted on the polyolefin chains [8].

In the present communication we report on the characterization of systems obtained by reactive blending of maleic anhydride grafted PP (PP-g-MA) and POSS functionalized with amino groups (NH₂-POSS) (Figure 1). Samples of PP homopolymer with same POSS components and ternary composites – with PP and PP-g-MA matrix - were also examined for comparison. The influence of processing conditions and POSS grafting

reaction on the morphological characteristics, crystallization kinetics, melting and degradation behaviour of the samples was investigated with the aim of studying the effect of the dispersed POSS nanoparticles on the nucleation, growth and lamellar structure of polymer crystals.

Figure 1. Melt grafting reaction of NH₂-POSS onto PP-g-MA

EXPERIMENTAL PART

Isotactic polypropylene (PP) (Moplen HP501L, Basell,) and maleic anhydride grafted PP (PP-g-MA) (Polybond 3200, 1 wt.% MA, Crompton Corp.) were used as matrix polymers. Fully alkyl substituted POSS ($p=8$) with different alkyl groups, namely octamethyl- POSS (om-POSS), octaisobutyl-POSS (oib-POSS) and eptaisobutyl-amino-POSS (NH₂-POSS) (Hybrid Plastics) were employed as fillers. Binary (PP-g-MA/oib-POSS, PP-g-MA/NH₂-POSS, PP/NH₂-POSS,) and ternary (PP/PP-g-MA/NH₂-POSS) composites - with POSS content of 5 wt.% and 1-2.5 wt.% respectively – were supplied by the Centre for Engineering of Plastic Materials, Polytechnic of Turin (Alessandria, Italy). The samples were prepared by melt blending in a Brabender internal mixer and DSM miniextruder at 180°C. Neat PP-g-MA and PP were processed under the same conditions.

The morphology of blends was examined on the surfaces of bulk samples and films freeze-fractured in liquid nitrogen; the samples were sputter-coated with a fine layer of gold in an Edward sputter coater and analysed with a Jeol T300 scanning electron microscope. Energy dispersive X-ray spectrometry (EDS) was used to demonstrate the presence of POSS aggregates on the fracture surfaces of samples without coating treatment.

FTIR spectra of films of composites and plain components, obtained by compression moulding at 170/180 °C, were recorded in the 4000–400 cm⁻¹ frequency range by means of a Perkin-Elmer Spectrum One FTIR spectrophotometer equipped with a Perkin Elmer Spectrum Spotlight imaging system. Wide- and small angle X-ray scattering (WAXS, SAXS) analysis of PP composites was performed at room temperature with DRON-20 diffractometer connected with a Phillips generator operating at 50 kV and 30 mA, using the CuK α radiation ($\lambda= 0.1546$ nm). The long period values were estimated from the Lorentz-corrected sections of the 2-D SAXS patterns by the Bragg law.

The thermal behaviour of all materials was examined with a Pyris Diamond DSC (Perkin-Elmer) at a heating/cooling rate of 10 °C/min, under nitrogen flow. The samples (5–10 mg) were first heated to 190 °C for 2 min, then cooled to room temperature and again heated up to 190 °C (2nd heating run). Temperatures and heats of transition were measured at the max and from the areas of the crystallization/melting peaks. The isothermal crystallization kinetics of PP/POSS and PP/PP-g-MA/POSS samples were analysed by DSC in the temperature range 125-135 °C. The samples were first melted up to 190 °C at 10 °C/min, kept at this temperature for 5 min in order to erase any previous thermal history and then rapidly cooled (100 °C/min) to a prefixed T_c , recording the heat of crystallization as a function of time. For all processes the relative weight fraction $X(t)$ of material crystallized after time t was evaluated by the ratio of the crystallization area at the time t over the total area. The crystallization half-time, $t_{0.5}$, was taken as the time corresponding to $X(t)=0.5$. The melting behaviour of the isothermally crystallized samples was analysed by heating the samples directly from T_c up to 190°C in DSC at a rate of 10°C/min. The crystallinity degree X_c was evaluated from the ratio $\Delta H_m/\Delta H_m^\circ$ where $\Delta H_m^\circ=189$ J/g for PP [9]. Thermal degradation of composites and pure components was analysed with a TGA MK2 (Rheometric Scientific) in the range from 50° to 800 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min, both in N₂ atmosphere and air.

RESULTS

The morphology of the various systems was examined by SEM on samples crystallized from the melt both in dynamic and isothermal conditions. All samples exhibited the characteristic spherulitic morphology of isotactic polypropylene. For non-reactive composites containing fully alkyl substituted POSS (PP-g-MA/oib-POSS, PP/oib-POSS) SEM analysis of freeze fractured surfaces showed a phase separation of the filler with formation of large aggregates of micron size in interspherulitic regions (Figure 2a), as well as the presence of regular platelet-like POSS crystals at the spherulite borders in isothermally crystallized samples (Figure 2b). Similar textures were detected for the binary system of PP with NH₂-POSS [10].

Figure 2. SEM micrograph of (a) PP/oib-POSS (95/5) and (b) PP-g-MA/oib-POSS (95/5) isothermally crystallized at $T_c = 130^\circ\text{C}$.

Observation by optical microscopy on composites of PP with fully alkyl substituted POSS (om-POSS, oib-POSS) had shown that the growth of PP spherulites was nucleated on the surfaces of POSS crystals [6]. Otherwise, composites with reactive components (PP-g-MA/NH₂-POSS, PP/PP-g-MA/NH₂-POSS) did not show any presence of POSS crystal aggregates, indicating a fine dispersion of the filler into the polymer matrix (Figure 3), as confirmed by the results of EDS microanalysis (weak Si peaks at 1.7 keV). This supported the occurrence of grafting reactions of the amino modified POSS onto PP-g-MA chains.

Figure 3. SEM micrograph of isothermally crystallized PP-g-MA/NH₂-POSS (95/5) sample ($T_c = 130^\circ\text{C}$).

Accordingly, WAXS spectra of non-reactive systems (PP-g-MA/oib-POSS, PP/NH₂-POSS) displayed intense reflections characteristic of POSS crystals in 2θ range $6 \pm 12^\circ$, while no significant signals relevant to POSS crystalline structures were detected in the

case of reactive PP-g-MA/NH₂-POSS sample (Figure 4). Moreover, it must be noticed that the appearance of POSS reflections is accompanied by the formation of γ phase PP crystals (peak at $2\theta=20.07^\circ$). The growth of γ form crystals of PP has been also observed in melt crystallized blends containing PP functionalized with carboxyl groups interacting with polyamide or polyester chains [11].

Figure 4. WAXS spectra of melt crystallized composites and plain polymers: (1) PP-g-MA; (2) PP-g-MA/oib-POSS; (3) PP-g-MA/NH₂-POSS; (4) PP/NH₂-POSS; (5) PP/PP-g-MA/ NH₂-POSS (50/47.5/2.5); (6) PP/PP-g-MA/NH₂-POSS (75/23.5/1.25); 7) PP.

The thermal behaviour of the composites resulted to be influenced by the chemical structure of the components and phase morphology. DSC thermograms showed that on cooling (10°/min) from the melt the crystallization temperature of PP-g-MA (113.6 °C) increased on addition of oib-POSS (118.5 °C) but decreased in the presence of

Figure 5. Relative crystallinity fraction as a function of crystallization time at $T_c = 130^\circ\text{C}$ for PP-g-MA/POSS and plain PP-g-MA.

NH₂-POSS (111.0 °C). This behaviour can be related to the degree of POSS dispersion within the polymer matrix, giving rise to crystal nucleation effects at low dispersion of the filler, or to retarded crystallization when it is highly dispersed due to the chemical interactions between the components.

The isothermal crystallization kinetics of both functionalized and non-functionalized samples were examined in the temperature range 122-135°C according to the Avrami model:

$$X(t) = 1 - \exp(-K_n t^n)$$

where $X(t)$ is the fraction of polymer crystallized at time t , n an exponent depending on the type of nucleation and growth geometry of the crystals and K_n the kinetic constant [12].

Values of n and K_n were determined from the slope and the intersection of linear plots of $\log[-\ln(1-X_t)]$ vs. $\log t$, respectively. The overall crystallization rate (i.e., the reciprocal of crystallization half-time) of PP-*g*-MA matrix was found to decrease in the composites with NH₂-POSS, as compared to plain PP-*g*-MA (Figure 5). On the other side the crystallization rate of PP-*g*-MA increased in composites with oib-POSS.

Figure 6. Crystallization half-time of plain polymers and their composites with NH₂-POSS as a function of isothermal crystallization temperature.

For samples containing NH₂-POSS, the values of the Avrami exponent ($n=3.5-4$) were higher than those recorded for neat PP-*g*-MA and PP-*g*-MA/oib-POSS ($n= 3$), supporting that the primary nucleation and the growth of polymer crystals are strictly affected by the interactions between the components, and thus by POSS dispersion. The large decrease of the overall crystallization rate recorded in the case of PP-*g*-MA/NH₂-POSS sample (Figure 6) is likely a consequence of the polymer-nanoparticles interactions in the melt, as well as of constrains caused by POSS grafting on the polypropylene chains [13]. On the other side, the increase observed in the presence of oib-POSS is to be ascribed to nucleating effect of POSS crystals [6].

Figure 7. DSC melting thermograms of (a) PP-*g*-MA/oib-POSS and (b) PP/NH₂-POSS isothermally crystallized at various T_c .

The analysis of melting behaviour of isothermally crystallized samples showed the occurrence of multiple melting peaks that could be ascribed to crystals of different stability and structure (polymorphic α and γ forms) and to reorganization phenomena during heating. The presence of β form crystals was detected only for plain PP samples. In Figures 8a-b the values of the observed melting temperatures (low and high melting peak) of PP/NH₂-POSS and PP-*g*-MA/NH₂-POSS composites are plotted as a linear function of crystallization temperature, according to Hoffmann-Week equation [14]:

$$T_m = T_m^\circ(\psi-1)/\psi + T_c/\psi$$

where ψ is a parameter related to the fold length of primary nuclei. A significant change of the equilibrium melting temperature T_m° (extrapolated to the line $T_m=T_c$) of PP-*g*-MA crystals was noticed for the reactive samples in the presence of NH₂-POSS ($T_m^\circ=177.0^\circ\text{C}$ for PP-*g*-MA, 176°C for PP-*g*-MA/oib-POSS and 172.5°C for PP-*g*-MA/NH₂-POSS; for plain PP $T_m^\circ=185^\circ\text{C}$) suggesting that the filler nanoparticles were dispersed

within the interlamellar amorphous region of the spherulites. Accordingly, the results of SAXS analysis showed that the lamellar thickness of polymer crystals was influenced by the sample composition and crystallization conditions, and the estimated values of crystal thickness were lowered in the case of reactive system [15].

Figure 8. DSC melting temperatures of isothermally crystallized samples vs. T_c for: (a) PP-g-MA/oib-POSS, (b) PP-g-MA/NH₂-POSS. (●): high-melting peak; (■): low-melting peak.

The degradation behaviour of PP-g-MA/POSS, PP/POSS and PP/PP-g-MA/POSS samples was examined in the temperature range 100-600 °C both in nitrogen gas and in air (Figure 9). In nitrogen, all samples displayed the same trend almost independently of POSS functionalization. In air, a different behaviour was observed for PP-g-MA/NH₂-POSS which presented a large shift (about 90 °C) of the temperature of maximum weight loss rate as compared to PP-g-MA/oib-POSS and plain PP-g-MA (as well as PP homopolymer), thus indicating that the dispersed POSS component greatly improved the stability of the polyolefin toward thermoxidative degradation. This effect can be

explained in terms of accumulation of grafted POSS on the sample surface during the oxidation process, giving rise to the formation of a ceramic phase which acts as a protective barrier [16, 17].

Figure 9. Derivative weight loss from TGA analysis of PP/POSS composites and plain polymers in air.

CONCLUSIONS

Polyolefin/POSS hybrids based on PP-*g*-MA matrix and amino functionalized POSS, as dispersed component, display marked changes of morphology, structure and phase behaviour as compared to non functionalized PP/POSS systems. Grafting reactions of amino modified POSS onto maleated PP chains can be effectively exploited by melt mixing to promote the dispersion of POSS cages at molecular level, enhancing the properties and performances of these systems. The reported results pointed out that the crystallization behaviour and the crystal superstructure of the polyolefin matrix are strictly influenced by the POSS dispersion. Fully alkyl substituted POSS in PP-*g*-MA (and PP) matrix give rise to phase separation phenomena and nucleating effects, increasing the overall crystallization rate of polypropylene, while in the reactive PP-*g*-MA/NH₂-POSS system a marked decrease of the polymer crystallization rate is found as a consequence of the POSS grafting reactions. The molecular dispersion of grafted POSS is responsible for the neat improvement of thermal stability of the functionalized composites toward oxidative degradation.

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